

Evaluating the Prediction Ability of Using Earth Observation Technology to Monitor Soil Organic Carbon in Comparison to Soil Map

Christiana O. Isaac-Izoya

Technische Hochschule Bingen

Submitted on: 26/02/2025

Disclaimer: This is a preprint version of my master's thesis submitted to Technische Hochschule Bingen. The final version may be subject to further revisions.

For inquiries, please contact: obeiisaac@yahoo.com

Abstract

The increasing demand for soil-derived ecosystem services necessitates reliable data on soil resources to support sustainable land management. Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) is a key indicator of soil quality, influencing essential biological, chemical, and physical soil functions, such as nutrient cycling, water retention, and soil structure maintenance. This study employs remote sensing and GIS-based Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) techniques to model SOC distribution across different landscapes.

A combination of remote sensing and soil data was used for statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics, t-tests, Anova, correlation and regression analysis. Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter data (VV polarization) was utilized for soil moisture estimation, while Sentinel-2 vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI), Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Landsat 8 Land Surface Temperature, and SoilGrids-derived parameters (sand, clay, pH, nitrogen) were integrated. The SOC reference data was obtained from the Landesamt für Geologie und Bergbau Rheinland-Pfalz (LGB).

The study was conducted in three geographical locations in the Bingen am Rhein region of Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany: Budesheim (lowland), Waldhagelsheim (hills), and Fulder Aue-Ilmen (near the Rhine River). Results indicate significant spatial variability in SOC distribution, with the highest variability observed in the Rhine region. This variation is likely influenced by differences in soil types, which affect water retention, organic matter accumulation, and mineral composition. The findings highlight the importance of integrating remote sensing techniques for SOC monitoring, offering valuable insights for sustainable soil management.